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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Real-time Event Distribution Network brought to openly accessible “product grade level”

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ABSTRACT

This document describes, how the “Real-time Event Distribution Network” (REDNet) has been transferred to market in the frame of the H2020 co-funded ARIES project. The document presents a website that company Cosylab uses now to promote the product on a broad scale. It also highlights first customers who adopted either the architecture, the design or the entire product, which also comprises hardware and software elements. This deliverable demonstrates a tangible impact that this H2020 project created and how technology has been effectively transferred from fundamental physics research carried out at CERN to market as a co-construction process with Cosylab.

**REAL-TIME EVENT DISTRIBUTION NETWORK
BROUGHT TO OPENLY ACCESSIBLE PRODUCT
GRADE LEVEL**

Deliverable: D14.5

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ARIES Consortium, 2018-2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730871. ARIES began in May 2017 and will run for 4 years.

All original knowledge and documentation that form a basis for the development of the main timing system described in this document are made available by CERN in compliance with Agreement KR2954/KT/BE/007/A. CERN uses its IP to co-develop with Cosylab the requirements and the architecture of a generic particle accelerator main timing system that aims at being used in academic, industrial and medical application domains. The specified system will be implemented, packaged and distributed by Cosylab. © CERN-EBG MedAustron 2014. All rights not expressly granted reserved.

Delivery Slip

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. SCOPE	5
2. OVERVIEW	5
2.1 SYSTEM DESCRIPTION	5
2.2 COMPONENTS	7
3. PRODUCT PROMOTION	8
3.1 WEBSITE DESCRIPTION	8
3.2 WEBSITE CONTENTS	11
4. EARLY ADOPTERS	14
4.1 PRODUCT SUMMARY	14
4.2 ADOPTERS	15
5. REFERENCES	16

Executive summary

This document summarises how the REDNet (“Realtime Event Distribution Network”) main timing system that has originally been conceived by CERN in the MedAustron project has been developed into a market-ready product by company Cosylab. The document highlights the website that Cosylab has built to introduce and market their new timing system product line. The document gives a brief overview of the main building blocks of the system. The document also highlights first customers who adopted either the architecture, the design or even the entire product line as a backbone of their developments.

Technical documents and an implementation specifically for that project have been co-constructed by companies Cosylab (contracted by MedAustron), by MedAustron personnel and by CERN personnel. Following agreement KR2954/KT/BE007/A between EBG MedAustron GmbH and CERN, CERN used its knowledge and documentation to co-develop with Cosylab the requirements and architecture for a generic particle accelerator main timing system in the scope of the ARIES H2020 project. This new architecture and design is made available in Open Access format under the H2020 rules as a cooperative effort of CERN and Cosylab and serves as a basis for a new implementation by Cosylab, which is truly project neutral and which can serve the world-wide particle accelerator community for the benefits of the entire society.

The final product is offered, further developed and marketed by Cosylab.

This deliverable demonstrates an effective transfer of technology from fundamental physics research to market via an EC funded co-construction process. This achievement marks therefore the creation of tangible, substantial and lasting impact of a H2020 EC project for society and industry.

1. Scope

The ARIES project promotes the transfer of knowledge from developments carried out in the frame of fundamental physics research with particle accelerators to industry and society. One excellent example for this activity is the development of a generic particle accelerator main timing system that originates from concepts, architectures and designs that emerged from works in the frame of the Large Hadron Collider and Compact Muon Solenoid experiment projects. It led to the development of a timing system for the MedAustron medical accelerator project at CERN under the guidance of CERN. An agreement between CERN and the operating company EBG MedAustron made it possible to further leverage this work and to base the development of an open timing system for the entire particle accelerator community on these development works.

This document reports on how the system that has been developed into a product line by company Cosylab as a timing system for small to medium sized particle accelerators aiming at medical and industrial applications is offered and promoted by the company. The product is based on original work that has been carried out at CERN. It accompanies the ongoing co-innovation process between CERN and company Cosylab. The document also presents the current bill of material as a “system in the box” appliance.

2. Overview

2.1 SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

This section describes briefly the real-time event distribution network (REDNet) based main timing system, which is developed in this project and which is now marketed as a product by Cosylab under the name C-MTS. The system is used to coordinate the activities of particle accelerator devices. At hardware-level, the system comprises a main timing event generator (MTG), several main timing event receivers (MTR) and communication links connecting the individual components. At software level, the system includes all non-real time software to configure and operate the MTG, all real-time and embedded software needed to achieve the approved functional and non-functional requirements as well as API components that application designers can use at the receiver side to implement actions in response to received timing events.

The role of the real-time event distribution network is to coordinate the activity of all individual accelerator components in order to produce beams of the particle accelerator.

Operations that are specific to the individual accelerator components under control are implemented in the equipment under control (EUC) that resides on the receiver side, by generating actions at precisely defined points in time. The main timing system provides the functionality to perform these front-end control and processing actions in a synchronized way. For this purpose, the baseline architecture is a centralized one, providing a real-time broadcast network based on a tree-topology (see system topology Figure 1 below).

Figure 1: Timing system topology.

The system synchronizes the front-end control devices of the particle accelerator by broadcasting timing events from the main timing generator (MTG) to multiple main timing receivers (MTR). Each equipment under control (EUC) that needs to receive events from the system hosts a MTR hardware device.

General functions that the real-time event distribution network provides are:

- Emission of timing events to receiver components
- Emission of commands to receiver components
- Emission of asynchronous user events to receiver components
- Concurrent generation of accelerator cycles for virtual accelerators (a.k.a. execution slots)
- Generation of responses to received timing events
- Synchronized generation of accelerator cycles to a specified time grid
- Synchronization of the entire system to a high-precision GPS 100 MHz clock

2.2 COMPONENTS

A detailed bill of materials has been included in document MS48. This section gives a brief overview of the system as built.

Component	Type or description	Weblink
Generator / Receiver Chassis	NI PXIe-1082	http://www.ni.com/sl-si/support/model.pxie-1082.html
Generator / Receiver Controller	NI PXIe-8840 controller	http://www.ni.com/sl-si/support/model.pxie-8840.html
Optic Cable	Fibre optic cable LC-LC duplex multimode 850 nm	n/a
SFP Optical Transceivers	AVAGO AFBR-57R5APZ	http://www.mrf.fi/
Generator card	PXIe-EVG-300 (JTP V1.2)	http://www.mrf.fi/
Receiver card	PXIe-EVR-300 (JTP V1.2)	http://www.mrf.fi/
Concentrator chassis	CompactPCI chassis (CompactPCI 2 U pn. 24579-081)	https://schroff.nvent.com/en/schroff/compact-pci-system/compactpci-2%20u--4-slot--with%20rear-i-o-and-atx-power-supply-24579-081
Concentrator card	cPCI-FCT-8	http://www.mrf.fi/index.php/compactpci-products/82-compactpci-fan-out-concentrator-cpci-fct-8
Receiver TTL output	TTL Output UNIV-TTL	http://www.mrf.fi/index.php/universal-io-modules/84-universal-io-ttl-output-univ-ttl
Generator TTL input	TTL Input UNIV-TTLIN	http://www.mrf.fi/index.php/universal-io-modules/83-universal-io-ttl-input-univ-ttlin

3. Product promotion

3.1 WEBSITE DESCRIPTION

This section reproduces elements from the website that Cosylab has set up at

<https://www.cosylab.com/main-timing-system/>

to promote the product that is a direct result of the ARIES Research and Innovation Action to facilitate the promoting of the technology.

Cosylab set up a dedicated webpage to present the result of the collaboration that took place in the frame of the H2020 funded project. The webpage was published as part of the Cosylab main website. The page dedicated to the timing system had been prepared a special area to present to interested professionals, potential clients, and a general, technically interested audience the result of the project and the upgrade of it within the next stages of the product development.

The webpage has the following contents elements:

Purpose:

The purpose of the webpage is to present the project results, the creation of a modular particle accelerator main timing system that can be easily adapted to different use cases. Additionally, we will use this page also to present an upgrade of that system, the foreseeable next stages of the development and potential future results beyond the H2020 funded EU project. The main purpose of the webpage is the promotion of these newly developed products that emerge from the initial system development.

The idea of the webpage is to publish all the results from the collaboration in this work package and to present the work to a broad audience. In this way, we want to inform potential customers about a new product. Cosylab has integrated also pictures of the product on the page to re-assure potential clients about the maturity of the development. The system is ready for use in a variety of particle accelerator environments and has already been adopted by selected projects as a control system backbone.

The webpage includes important documents that result from the collaboration in the frame of the H2020 project and that were prepared during the ARIES project period. Most notably, the site makes available the “Accelerator Timing System Reviewed Requirements Document” and the “Reviewed design and system configuration, updated software” document.

Product presentation:

Cosylab brands the system, originally called “REDNet” (Realytime Event Distribution Network) as C-MTS. It is built on well-proven, scalable and extensible technologies such as National Instruments PXIe computing equipment and Micro-Research-Finland (MRF) timing hardware. The technology can be easily integrated with numerous platforms, ranging from VME to cPCI industrial computing equipment, PLCs and low-level electrical and optical signalling technologies (e.g. TTL, ECL, SFP, LVDS).

C-MTS is based on the technology developments on a "Reliable Event Distribution Network" (REDNet) in the frame of a cooperation between CERN, Cosylab and MedAustron between 2008 and 2014. The technology has been disclosed during the development and has been made openly available in the frame of this EU project to create societal benefits in a variety of application fields.

Figure 2: Exemplar installation of the system in a single rack.

Contact person:

As Cosylab is aware of the importance of personal presentation and contacts as well as the need for a contact person and to discuss questions regarding the development and project results as well as the future product development, Cosylab included contact details on the webpage. The contact, provided on the page, has excellent knowledge about the project and technical development. This contact person, Gregor Cijan, has been actively working on the project and is a project manager and lead developer at Cosylab. His email and telephone number have been published on the webpage, so he can be contacted by any interested partners or customers. With his expertise he will help also commercialize the project results and present them to all the potentially interested people.

Contact e-mail: gregor.cijan@cosylab.com.

Future plans:

In the future, Cosylab will enrich the page with system development and upgrade information. After the EU project period, Cosylab plans also to prepare and include video material about the product and also some interviews with our customers, who will report about their experience with the product.

EU funding acknowledgement:

In line with the EC H2020 regulations, Cosylab has published on the webpage the funding acknowledgement: “The project, ARIES, has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under Grant Agreement No 730871. Background knowledge and documentation for this product development activity have been made available by CERN.”

Finally, Cosylab has included on the page also the ARIES project logo and the EU flag. On the webpage, Cosylab included also the link to the ARIES project webpage, and links to ARIES milestones and deliverables. With these links we are connecting the new page with the official project page.

Official ARIES project page: <https://aries.web.cern.ch>

ARIES milestones: <https://aries.web.cern.ch/milestones>

Link to ARIES deliverables: <https://aries.web.cern.ch/deliverables>

3.2 WEBSITE CONTENTS

This section re-produces selected contents from the product website that has been set up in the frame of this EU project. The contents status is April 2021.

Figure 3: Timing system webpage main contents area.

BENEFITS OF C-MTS

Figure 4: Section of the web page that contains clickable tiles, providing further detailed information about selected product features.

C-MTS Foundations

C-MTS is built on well-proven, scalable and extensible technologies such as the National Instruments PXIe computing equipment and Micro-Research-Finland (MRF) timing hardware, ensuring exact synchronization.

The technology can be easily integrated with numerous platforms, ranging from VME to cPCI industrial computing equipment, PLCs and low-level electrical and optical signalling technologies (e.g. TTL, ECL, SFP, LVDS).

C-MTS is based on the technology development of the "Reliable Event Distribution Network" (REDNet) in the frame of the cooperation between CERN, Cosylab and MedAustron between 2008 and 2014. The technology was disclosed during the development and has been made openly available through the ARIES EU project (Grant Agreement No. 7308761) inside the Horizon 2020 programme to create societal benefits in various application fields.

The initial adoption of the technology by other particle accelerator projects (ADAM LIGHT, MYRRHA) demonstrate its flexibility and the capability to scale from small to large deployments with ease.

As Johannes Gutieber from CERN underlines: "*The CERN – Cosylab cooperation in conceiving a general timing system technology is a great showcase of transfer from knowledge from fundamental particle physics research to society*".

- More about project's milestones you can find: <https://aries.web.cern.ch/milestones>
- More about project's deliverables you can find: <https://aries.web.cern.ch/deliverables>

About the results prepared in the document **Accelerator Timing System Reviewed Requirements Document** and in the document **Reviewed design and system configuration, updated software**.

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Figure 5: Area of the web page that provides some background information about the product development and that provides the contact information for potentially interested clients.

4. Early adopters

4.1 PRODUCT SUMMARY

The main timing system product, which is a result of this EU project, is a system to synchronize the operation of hundreds of devices distributed across the particle accelerator with high time accuracy down to the nanosecond range. Cosylab's timing system is an off-the-shelf product, based on Micro-Research Finland and National Instruments hardware technologies with in-house developed extensions that are part of the product line. The system is adaptable to the needs of particle therapy and research particle accelerators of varying types (linear and circular) and sizes (from in-room to several kilometers).

The main C-MTS design features are:

- Developed in the Cosylab provided, so called "MADIE" software framework for seamless integration with other devices developed in the same framework. It **supports industry standard hardware and software interfaces** including **interfaces to medical systems and a variety of SCADA systems**.
- A central, high-precision source of clock, triggers, and time for synchronizing operation of devices and precise data timestamping and timestamp distribution.
- A **distributed and scalable system** capable of running a virtually limitless number of receivers and ensuring that **all timing receivers are phase-locked** to the timing generator avoiding the problem of phase drift by design.
- **Real-time data distribution and fast acknowledging mechanism** ensure speed and reliability during medical treatments, where lowering energy switching time directly impacts the treatment time, increasing overall patient throughput.

The central timing system provides **timing event distribution and a data link** from timing generators to receivers and vice versa (downstream and upstream). These features are implemented using the PXIe backplane and a real-time optical network. Response interfaces, available on the event receivers and support for virtual accelerators are also given.

Cosylab is offering this product to different customers today and is selling the solution as a product. At the same time, **Cosylab also offers to customers the option of tailoring the solution** in line with their specifications and requests.

4.2 ADOPTERS

Advanced Oncotherapy is a specialist developer and provider of a breakthrough proton therapy system, the LIGHT system, which is the result of 25 years of work with CERN and ADAM S.A. (Meyrin, Geneva). LIGHT will provide active energy modulation, fast beam intensity, and energy change as well as modularity and reduced shielding.

Company ADAM S.A. has adopted the ARIES development for the design and construction of a novel linear particle accelerator for image-guided hadron therapy.

The developments in the scope of ARIES from the baseline for the development of the system, which are subject to a dedicated contract between ADAM S.A. and Cosylab. The company Cosylab had already developed and modified the solution in line with the customer's specification and had successfully delivered the solution to ADAM S.A.

Cosylab has identified several further customers that can benefit from the use of this solution, and with all of them, Cosylab has already started the communication. With some of them, Cosylab is today in the phase of contract negotiations. Therefore no further information about these clients can be published in this EU project deliverable.

These achievements mark therefore the creation of tangible, substantial, and lasting impact of an H2020 EC project for society and industry.

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